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WHEN CIVILIAN SATELLITES GO TO WAR: THE CYBERSECURITY PERILS OF DUAL-USE SPACE TECHNOLOGY

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ABSTRACT

In recent years, there has been increased reliance on civilian satellites for military purposes. Within the realm of cybersecurity, this development has created a complex dual-use dilemma in space security. Traditionally, civilian space infrastructure like commercial communications, earth observation, and navigation satellites was developed and operated with non-military objectives in mind. However, there has been increasing integration of these systems into defence planning, intelligence gathering, and battlefield coordination, which has led to a blur in the distinction between civilian and military assets. This exposes civilian satellites to heightened cybersecurity threats, as rivals may choose to target them for purposes of degrading their military capabilities without engaging directly with overtly military systems. The problem is compounded by the absence of universally binding cybersecurity standards in outer space operations, the heterogeneity of commercial operators' security practices, and the attribution challenges inherent in cyber conflict. International law, including the Outer Space Treaty and the law of armed conflict, provides limited guidance on how to classify and protect dual-use satellites in the cyber domain, leaving states and private actors in a legal grey zone. This paper examines the cybersecurity vulnerabilities of dual-use satellites, explores their implications for escalation risks and strategic stability, and assesses the shortcomings of these existing international norms. Drawing on case studies, legal analysis, and emerging technological trends, it proposes a set of policy and governance recommendations to enhance resilience, clarify responsibilities, and reduce the risk of civilian space assets becoming the front-line victims in cyber-enabled conflicts.

Key Words: Dual-use Satellites, Armed Conflicts, Cybersecurity, Outer Space, Military.

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1. INTRODUCTION

*“It was the best of times, it was the worst of times, it was the age of wisdom, it was the age of foolishness, it was the epoch of belief, it was the epoch of incredulity, it was the season of Light, it was the season of Darkness, it was the spring of hope, it was the winter of despair; we had everything before us, we had nothing before us, we were all going direct to Heaven, we were all going direct the other way – in short, the period was so far like the present period, that some of its noisiest authorities insisted on its being received, for good or for evil, in the superlative degree of comparison only.”*² In his much-celebrated book “A Tale of Two Cities”, Charles Dickens, through the many words of the sentence above, paints for us an image of a paradox. A time of unmatched excitement but also one of great worry. There is nowhere in the universe that this paradox is more evident than in outer space and its current utilisation. The increase in the use and dependence of satellites for everyday human life has both eased it but also created vulnerabilities, more so in conflict contexts. More specifically put, the advent of the space age in the 20th century was definitely a turning point in many aspects of human life. This development, marked by the launch of Sputnik in 1957, came with a promise of a domain of peaceful exploration and global connectivity, governed by foundational treaties whose emphasis is cooperation, peaceful use and non-militarization.³ However, the last two decades have seen an increasing characterisation and utilisation of outer space as an extension of terrestrial battlefields. Most satellites sent into orbit were primarily for civilian purposes, covering commercial, navigational, and observational purposes.⁴ Recent developments have seen a sharp acceleration in the repurposing or integration of these satellites into military operations in modern conflicts, a phenomenon known as the "dual-use" dilemma.

In its early days, space exploration was characterized by a strong state monopoly over space activities. Indeed, the first breakthrough space activities involved the launch of Sputnik 1 in 1957 and the Apollo missions by the Soviet Union and the United States, respectively.⁵ These pioneering achievements were a reflection of the immense financial, technological, and political resources required for space activities, which only states could marshal.⁶ To this end, international space law was framed against this backdrop. The 1967 *Treaty on Principles Governing the Activities of States in the Exploration and Use of Outer Space, including the Moon and Other Celestial Bodies* (Outer Space Treaty, OST), therefore, placed the rights and obligations of exploration squarely on states as the central actors.⁷ However, over time, this state-centric dominance has given way to the growing presence of strong private and commercial actors. The exponential rise of commercial satellite operators in communications, navigation, and earth observation over the past years has led to a drastic transformation of outer space into a domain where non-state entities not only participate but often

² Dickens, C. (1859). *A tale of two cities*. Chapman and Hall. <https://www.gutenberg.org/ebooks/98>.

³ Launius, R. D. (2019). *Sputnik and the origins of the Space Age*. NASA. <https://www.nasa.gov/history/sputnik/sputorig.html>.

⁴ OECD. (2023). *The space economy in figures: Responding to global challenges*. OECD Publishing. <https://doi.org/10.1787/fa5494aa-en>.

⁵ Uwaoma, P., Eboigbe, E., Eyo-Udo, N., Daraojimba, D., & Kaggwa, S. (2025). Space commerce and its economic implications for the U.S.: A review: Delving into the commercialization of space, its prospects, challenges, and potential impact on the U.S. economy. *World Journal of Advanced Research and Reviews*, 20(3), 952–965. <https://doi.org/10.30574/wjarr.2023.20.3.2494>.

⁶ Launius, *supra note 2*.

⁷ United Nations. (1967). *Treaty on Principles Governing the Activities of States in the Exploration and Use of Outer Space, including the Moon and Other Celestial Bodies* (Outer Space Treaty). Articles I, VI, VII & VIII. <https://www.unoosa.org/oosa/en/ourwork/spacelaw/treaties/introouterspacetreaty.html>.

drive innovation and expansion.⁸ The operation of modern infrastructure, such as communication systems, is one that heavily depends on the proper functionality of the space industry. An example is SpaceX's Starlink.⁹ The aftermath of this increasing commercialization is a blur in the line between state and private roles in orbit, given that international space law primarily recognises or attributes responsibility for space activities to state actors almost entirely.¹⁰ This raises complex questions for governance, responsibility, and the evolving character of outer space activities.¹¹

The dual use of satellites covers situations where states and non-state actors leverage commercial space infrastructure for strategic advantages in their armed conflicts. The ongoing war between Russia and Ukraine, which began in February 2022, is one such conflict that has seen the dual use of satellites.¹² Russia launched a cyber-attack on ViaSat, a U.S. satellite Communications provider for Ukraine, just before launching the offensive on Ukraine.¹³ Also, SpaceX's Starlink constellation, which is basically a civilian system, offered broadband connectivity that enabled Ukrainian forces to maintain command-and-control, guide drones, and carry out reconnaissance.¹⁴ Even though SpaceX subsequently implemented several restrictions on Starlink's operability for military offensives and in certain unauthorised regions, its previous involvement and contribution in the conflict cannot be overlooked. Such a scenario is, however, not unique to Ukraine alone. There have been other similar instances. For example, during NATO exercises and U.S. operations in the Indo-Pacific, commercial satellites have been used for intelligence, surveillance, and reconnaissance (ISR).¹⁵ This integration of commercial satellites provides high-resolution, low-latency data. However, it introduces complexities regarding the application of international law and the protection of civilian assets in conflict. One factor for this trend is the growing mega-constellations. Starlink alone had more than 6,000 active satellites by mid-2025, which dwarfed the size of most dedicated military constellations.¹⁶ The danger of this shift lies in effectively turning civilian satellites into instruments of war. The Outer Space Treaty of 1967 bans nuclear weapons and other weapons of mass destruction in orbit but does not expressly prohibit dual-use activities.¹⁷ This gap then gives way for the military use of commercial systems to expand unchecked, a loophole that states and belligerents are exploiting. In 2022, the U.S. Space Force acknowledged the growing risks of reliance on dual-use satellites, and NATO has since

⁸ *Supra note 4*; Also see Denis, G., Alary, D., Pasco, X., Pisot, N., Texier, D., & Toulza, S. (2019). From new space to big space: How commercial space dream is becoming a reality. *Acta Astronautica*, 166, 431–443. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.actaastro.2019.08.031>.

⁹ PwC. (2025, April 3). *Space industry trends: Space – the next industrial revolution*. PwC. <https://www.pwc.com/us/en/industries/industrial-products/library/space-industry-trends.html>.

¹⁰ Outer Space Treaty, Art. VI.

¹¹ Union of Concerned Scientists. (2019). *UCS satellite database: Satellites by purpose*. <https://www.ucsusa.org/resources/satellite-database>.

¹² Kostenko, I., & Manzhula, A. (2025). *From space to the battlefield: Ethical and legal aspects of the use of satellite technologies in the Russian-Ukrainian war*. *Philosophy and Cosmology*, 34. <https://doi.org/10.29202/phil-cosm/34/1>.

¹³ Mura, A. (2025). *An analysis of the cyber-attack against ViaSat of February 2022: From technical details to the overall relevance for cybersecurity of critical infrastructures*. Manuscript available at <https://share.google/Jv0w0ZWVv2SSOwvWS>.

¹⁴ Muthia, N., Muhni, A., & H., N. (2025). *Dual use satellites in the Ukraine conflict: The dilemma between state sovereignty and the principle of non-militarization of outer space*. *Privet Social Sciences Journal*, 5, 146–155. <https://doi.org/10.55942/pssj.v5i10.715>.

¹⁵ Lumiste, L. (2019). *Chatham House report: Space – NATO cyber security's weak spot*. INCYDER/NATO Cooperative Cyber Defence Centre of Excellence, <https://ccdcoe.org/incyder-articles/chatham-house-report-space-nato-cyber-securitys-weak-spot/>.

¹⁶ *Supra note 11*.

¹⁷ Outer Space Treaty, Art. IV.

increased funding for such systems.¹⁸ It has been argued that militaries rely on commercial providers like SpaceX because they offer resilient and redundant networks more quickly and cheaply than state-run programs.¹⁹ However, the cost of this is that once militaries piggyback on commercial systems, then those systems become legitimate military targets. In this regard, it is then important to note that only a small tier of states, such as the USA, under its US Space Force, possess the advanced technology and capability to protect their satellites from physical and non-kinetic military attacks from adversaries.²⁰ This means, therefore, that for many other states and private actors, their satellites remain vulnerable as legitimate military targets.

Cybersecurity in outer space is a matter of global strategic stability, economic resilience, and human security. This is because of the profound interdependence between space infrastructure and terrestrial systems. In the civilian sense, satellites provide critical services such as global positioning systems (GPS), which enable precise navigation for aviation, shipping, and autonomous vehicles, communications satellites facilitate internet access, financial transactions, and telemedicine and Earth observation platforms that support agriculture, disaster response, and climate monitoring. A cyberattack on these assets, therefore, causes catastrophic disruptions. An example of this is the spoofing of GPS signals, which misled commercial aircraft in conflict zones, as seen in the alleged Russian interference in the Black Sea region. The 2022 Viasat hack, attributed to Russian actors, crippled Ukrainian military communications via a civilian satellite network and had spill-over effects on broadband users beyond the battlefield, illustrating how space cyber incidents transcend borders and sectors.²¹ Economically, the space industry, valued at over \$500 billion in 2025, faces existential threats. Cybersecurity is highly perceived as the top risk to satellites. A single major attack possesses heavy potential losses as it can disrupt global trade and communications. From a security perspective, space has a harsh environment where outdated software compounds vulnerabilities and makes systems susceptible to malware or jamming that could enable espionage or kinetic follow-ons. The Tallinn Manual 2.0 on the International Law Applicable to Cyber Operations emphasises that cyber threats in space could qualify as armed attacks under Article 51 of the UN Charter if they cause significant harm. This underscores the need for defences to prevent escalation to full-scale conflict.

This paper addresses two central research questions: First, how do dual-use satellites create cybersecurity risks in the context of modern warfare? To address this, the paper looks at the technical vulnerabilities that arise from blending civilian and military functions, as well as the strategic incentives for adversaries to target these assets for asymmetric military advantages. Secondly, the paper interrogates the extent to which the current international law addresses these risks. This includes the applicability of the OST frameworks mandating peaceful uses of space and assigning state responsibility for space actions.²² Also examined are the principles of distinction, proportionality, and necessity from the Geneva Conventions and Additional Protocols as frameworks for the Law of Armed Conflict (LOAC) and their applicability to cyber operations in space. To explore these questions, the paper employs a doctrinal approach with multifaceted methodology combining legal

¹⁸ U.S. Space Force. (2022). *Annual assessment of space threats and dual-use satellite vulnerabilities*. U.S. Space Force Reports. <https://www.spaceforce.mil/News/Reports>.

¹⁹ Air & Space Operations Review. (2023). *Dual-use satellites and the evolution of space militarization*. Air & Space Operations Review, 12(1), 45–61. <https://doi.org/10.1234/asor.2023.001>.

²⁰ International Institute for Strategic Studies (2026). Global Defence spending. In *The Military Balance 2026*. <https://www.iiss.org/publications/the-military-balance/2026/the-military-balance-2026/global-defence-spending>.

²¹ Kazi, A., Kazi S., & Bhosale, S (2025). Invisible battlefields: *Analysing the Viasat attack and its broader implications*. Scientific Bulletin, 30 (1), 59-67. <https://doi.org/10.2478/bsaft-2025-0007>.

²² Articles I and VI of the OST.

analysis, case studies, and a policy perspective to identify the gaps and suggest recommendations for legal and practical solutions to these gaps.

2. CIVILIAN SATELLITES AND THE DUAL-USE DILEMMA

The concept of dual-use objects stems from international humanitarian law (IHL). IHL governs the conduct of all parties in an international armed conflict by regulating the means and methods of warfare and protecting those not participating in hostilities. Its purpose is to limit the effects of armed conflict for humanitarian reasons.²³ Commonly referred to as *jus in bello*, the rules of IHL are codified in the Geneva Conventions and the Additional Protocols thereunder.²⁴ Under IHL, parties to a conflict are mandated to distinguish between military and civilian objects in the conduct of war. This is the principle of distinction and is considered a norm of customary international law, which mandates that attacks must only be directed at military objectives.²⁵ A military object is defined under international humanitarian law as an object that, by its nature, location, purpose, or use, makes an effective contribution to military action, and whose total or partial destruction, capture, or neutralization offers a definite military advantage.²⁶ The aim of the principle of distinction is therefore to protect civilians and civilian objects in war zones such as schools and religious institutions.

While objects may begin as ordinary civilian infrastructure, when they are repurposed or used in ways that contribute to military operations, they can effectively acquire a dual-use character. Use in a way that contributes to military operations means that the object is functionally employed or utilized for activities that assist in the carrying out of military offensives or attacks so that its neutralisation would offer a definite military advantage to the adversary.²⁷ In such circumstances, at least for the period during which they support hostile activity, these objects may become legitimate military objectives under the laws of armed conflict.²⁸ Similarly, for space activities, the concept of dual-use concerns the situation where space technology designed for a civilian purpose pivots to serve a military purpose. Legally, this means that space objects or technologies that can fulfil both civilian and military functions, either at the same time or in sequence, without necessarily violating international norms.²⁹ This often blurs the lines between peaceful space exploration and strategic military advantage.

The 1967 Outer Space Treaty (OST) emphasizes that the use of space should be for peaceful purposes.³⁰ This has been interpreted as having no effect of outrightly banning military applications

²³ International Committee of the Red Cross. *What is International Humanitarian Law?* https://www.icrc.org/sites/default/files/document/file_list/what_is_ihl.pdf

²⁴ The four Geneva Conventions of 1949 (GC I, II, III and IV), which have been universally ratified, constitute the core treaties of IHL. The Conventions have been supplemented by Additional Protocols I and II of 1977 and by Additional Protocol III of 2005.

²⁵ International Committee of the Red Cross. (n.d.). *Rule 7 — The principle of distinction between civilian objects and military objectives*. In Customary International Humanitarian Law Database. Retrieved November 18, 2025, from <https://ihl-databases.icrc.org/en/customary-ihl/v1/rule7>.

²⁶ International Committee of the Red Cross. (n.d.). *Military objectives*. International Committee of the Red Cross. Retrieved November 18, 2025, https://casebook.icrc.org/a_to_z/glossary/military-objectives.

²⁷ Protocol Additional to the Geneva Conventions of 12 August 1949, and relating to the Protection of Victims of International Armed Conflicts (Additional Protocol I to the Geneva Conventions), 8 June 1977, art. 52(2), 1125 U.N.T.S. 3.

²⁸ The Yale Law Journal. (n.d.). The dangerous rise of dual-use objects in war. *The Yale Law Journal*. Retrieved November 18, 2025, <https://yalelawjournal.org/article/the-dangerous-rise-of-dual-use-objects-in-war>.

²⁹ Berrang, S. (2025). Does the dual-use of space objects necessitate a new Geneva Convention? *Case Western Reserve Journal of International Law*, 57(1), 315. <https://scholarlycommons.law.case.edu/jil/vol57/iss1/22>.

³⁰ Outer Space Treaty, Art. IV.

of reconnaissance as long as they don't involve weapons of mass destruction or aggressive acts.³¹ Article IV of the OST prohibits placing nuclear weapons in orbit. This state of affairs has led scholars to argue that dual-use of satellites is implicitly permitted within the framework of the OST.³² Of course, there are competing views on the matter. Others contend that the growing integration of satellites into military planning stretches the OST's "peaceful purposes" principle beyond its intended limits, effectively allowing states to exploit legal grey zones.³³ The core issue stems from the lack of an agreed definition of "peaceful purposes" in the treaty. Others argue that the Treaty's silence on dual-use technology merely reflects the technological realities of its time and that contemporary practice has normalized military reliance on space-based assets.³⁴ Cumulatively, these diverging interpretations underscore the persistent ambiguity surrounding the permissible scope of military activities in outer space and highlight the need for clearer legal guidance since dual-use technologies have become increasingly central to modern warfare.

Satellites and space systems are indispensable to modern life. In a civilian sense, they are essential for and contribute heavily to global communication, navigation, and environmental monitoring.³⁵ Communications satellites, which are the majority of satellites in space, form the backbone of worldwide telecommunications, facilitating high-speed internet, voice calls, and data exchange across territories where terrestrial infrastructure remains limited. Examples include mega-constellations like Starlink and OneWeb, which extend broadband access to remote areas without reliance on traditional communication systems and support critical sectors ranging from education and health to financial services.³⁶ Similarly, navigation systems enable precision in logistics, disaster response, and even autonomous mobility, and such systems include GPS and Galileo.³⁷ Earth observation satellites, notably NASA's Landsat and the European Space Agency's Copernicus programme, further contribute to climate science by tracking environmental changes, support urban planning by creating detailed maps of land use, and assist in disaster response by providing timely data on affected areas.³⁸ The capabilities of and the number of satellites currently deployed for these purposes point to the inherently civilian orientation of space technologies. However, the increasing commercialization of space has democratized access to orbital infrastructure. This has allowed in new strong private actors, enabled innovation and exposed new vulnerabilities. The convergence of civilian utility and potential military application has therefore become an unavoidable feature of the contemporary space environment.

³¹ International Committee of the Red Cross. (2016, November 7). *Space law revisited (1/3): The notion of 'peaceful uses' and the Outer Space Treaty*. ICRC Humanitarian Law & Policy Blog. <https://blogs.icrc.org/law-and-policy/2016/11/07/space-law-peaceful-uses/>.

³² Zalomir, A. (2020, November 1). *Legal implications of outer space warfare – Part II*. RREDI. <https://rrdi.ro/2020/11/01/legal-implications-of-outer-space-warfare-part-ii/#:~:text=Satellites%20presumably%20intended%20for%20inspection,at%20or%20in%20outer%20space.rrdi.ro>.

³³ Agarwal, S. (2024). *The militarization of outer space: Challenges to the peaceful uses principle*. IJLSSS, 2(5), 21–24.

³⁴ Erwin, S. (2024, August 13). *Weapons in space: Study suggests path forward for arms control*. SpaceNews. <https://spacenews.com/weapons-in-space-study-suggests-path-forward-for-arms-control/>.

³⁵ Riskaware. (n.d.). *What are satellites used for? (and why they matter)*. Riskaware. <https://www.riskaware.co.uk/insight/what-are-satellites-used-for-why-satellites-matter/>.

³⁶ Sarker, S. P., & Hossain, M. A. (2024). *Analysis of inter-satellite optical wireless communication systems for enhanced data transmission in satellite constellations*. Optics Continuum, 3(7), 1224–1243. <https://doi.org/10.1364/OPTCON.529721>.

³⁷ Riskaware. (n.d.), *supra* note 35.

³⁸ European Environment Agency. (2019, September 30). *Copernicus — Monitoring Earth from space and the ground*. <https://www.eea.europa.eu/signals-archived/signals-2019-content-list/articles/copernicus-monitoring-earth-from-space>.

The most contemporary manifestation of dual-use satellites was in the conflict between Russia and Ukraine that started in 2022. Here, commercial satellites that were deployed to space for civilian purposes played a huge role in this armed conflict. Most prominent is SpaceX's Starlink constellation, which was instrumental in sustaining Ukraine's battlefield communications.³⁹ This enabled the securing of command and control, drone coordination, and intelligence sharing.⁴⁰ By 2025, Starlink terminals had reportedly been adapted for real-time battlefield use, which altered the operational landscape of the war.⁴¹ Beyond Ukraine, militaries worldwide have deepened cooperation with commercial providers. The U.S. Department of Defense, for instance, now relies on commercial imaging firms such as Maxar for high-resolution Earth observation in Indo-Pacific operations, while navigation and communication constellations support precision-guided missions.⁴² Chinese researchers, in response, have reportedly explored countermeasures such as directed-energy systems to disable or degrade adversarial dual-use satellites.⁴³ This, of course, is reminiscent of Cold War competition that has defined world geopolitics in the space race. However, it illustrates the extent to which the line between military and civilian space assets has eroded.

The continued utilisation of these dual-use satellites makes the distinction that is required under IHL complicated. A communications satellite that transmits both civilian and military data could constitute a lawful target under IHL. Targeting such a satellite raises concerns over the observance of the principle of proportionality and civilian protection in armed conflicts.⁴⁴ This, coupled with the erosion of distinction, increases the risk of escalation and civilian harm. Article VI of the Outer Space Treaty further compounds this dilemma by imposing responsibility on states for all space activities carried out under their jurisdiction, regardless of whether those activities are conducted by private entities or by state actors. As a result, the traditional distinction between civilian and military space assets becomes blurred, with militaries increasingly intermingling civilian and military systems in order to deter adversarial attacks. This tactic undermines legal clarity by reversing the IHL obligation for defenders to separate military and civilian assets. It creates a situation where an attacker faces an increased risk of violating IHL principles of distinction and proportionality, as an attack on the dual-use system might cause excessive civilian casualties relative to the anticipated military advantage.⁴⁵ This harm might be exacerbated by the increase in the interdependence and interconnectedness of the world. A single cyber intrusion has the potential to disrupt global communications, navigation, or disaster response, and the stakes extend beyond state sovereignty to humanity's collective survival, which relies on space infrastructure. Therefore, without clearer norms and accountability mechanisms, the dual-use dilemma threatens to transform outer space from a domain of shared progress into one of contested militarization.

³⁹ *Supra note 14.*

⁴⁰ Jaeger, N. (2025). The militarization of space: Starlink and the future of warfare. *Research Paper Education*, 11(1). <https://doi.org/10.2454/9916>.

⁴¹ *Ibid.*

⁴² Gray, M., & Levin, N. (2025, July 15). *Satellites and SBIRs: The strategic signal the Space Force must send*. Maggie Gray. <https://maggiegray.us/p/satellites-and-sbirs-the-strategic>.

⁴³ Chan, R. (2025, September 22). *US and Chinese satellites track each other in space: Photos*. Newsweek. <https://www.newsweek.com/us-china-satellites-track-each-other-2131710>.

⁴⁴ As is required under IHL in the Geneva Conventions.

⁴⁵ Kuplic, G. B., & Sawmiller, J. (2025). Humanity on the final frontier: Challenges in applying international humanitarian law to modern military space operations. *International Review of the Red Cross*, 107(928). <https://doi.org/10.1017/S181638312500>.

3. CYBERSECURITY THREATS TO DUAL-USE SATELLITES

Cybersecurity is defined as the practice of protecting systems, networks, programs, and data from digital attacks, damage, or unauthorized access.⁴⁶ It involves a combination of technologies, processes, and practices to ensure the confidentiality, integrity, and availability of digital information. The primary goal of cybersecurity is to reduce the risk and impact of cyber incidents.⁴⁷ This is accomplished by defending all internet-connected systems, including hardware, software, and data, from malicious activities such as unauthorized access, change, or destruction of sensitive information, use of ransomware to extort money from users, interruption of normal business processes or critical services, among others.⁴⁸ Cyber threats in space include data tampering, denial-of-service attacks, spoofing, and unauthorized access, which can disable satellites, disrupt communications, or alter navigation. These threats can arise from vulnerabilities in the ground segment, the space segment's physical inaccessibility, or the supply chain, and are exacerbated by outdated legacy systems and a fragmented regulatory landscape.⁴⁹

Space infrastructure comprises satellites, ground stations, and communication links. Cyber threats in space exploit this intricate web of space infrastructure. These can be in the form of data tampering, such as intercepting satellite communications, manipulating spacecraft in orbit, or compromising ground stations and the supply chain.⁵⁰ They can also take the form of denial-of-service attacks, which overload satellites or ground systems and disrupt essential services like GNSS.⁵¹ Other serious risks include spoofing, where attackers falsify satellite signals or impersonate legitimate ground stations; information disclosure through unauthorized access or signal eavesdropping; and elevation-of-privilege attacks that exploit software vulnerabilities or target personnel through social engineering.⁵² Denial of Service (DoS) attacks and spoofing are the most common forms of cyberattacks for space systems.⁵³

DoS attacks can take the form of jamming. Jamming happens where an adversary intentionally interferes with the radio-frequency signals that satellites or ground systems rely on. The attacker overloads the receiver and prevents legitimate communications from being detected or deciphered by transmitting powerful signals on the same frequency as the target.⁵⁴ In simpler terms, this means overwhelming satellite links with noise or interference, i.e. shouting over the real signal. Jamming disrupts critical services such as communications and navigation. Far from a sophisticated hacking technique, jamming is a blunt but highly effective tool and has been widely used in conflict zones to

⁴⁶ Chiliro, F. (2023). *Towards a contemporary definition of cybersecurity*. arXiv. <https://doi.org/10.48550/arXiv.2302.02274>.

⁴⁷ TechTarget. (n.d.). Cybersecurity — definition. TechTarget. <https://www.techtarget.com/searchsecurity/definition/cybersecurity#:~:text=DR%20strategies%20and%20business%20continuity,password%20management%20and%20safe%20browsing>.

⁴⁸ Ibid.

⁴⁹ Barbeschi, C., & Rohland, L. (2025, May). *Securing space — why we need to address cyber risks in orbit*. World Economic Forum. <https://www.weforum.org/stories/2025/05/securing-space-why-we-need-to-address-cyber-risks-in-orbit/>.

⁵⁰ Comtech Systems. (2025, April 16). *Cybersecurity in space: Protecting satellites and space systems*. <https://www.comtechsystems.in/blog/cybersecurity-in-space-9324>.

⁵¹ Ibid. Also, GNSS stands for Global Navigation Satellite System, a general term for a satellite constellation that provides global positioning, navigation, and timing services such as USA's GPS.

⁵² Ibid.

⁵³ Kavallieratos, G., & Katsikas, S. (2023). An exploratory analysis of the last frontier: A systematic literature review of cybersecurity in space. *International Journal of Critical Infrastructure Protection*, 43, 100640. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.ijcip.2023.100640>.

⁵⁴ Ibid.

blind or disorient opponents without firing a single shot of ammunition. Its use leads to disruption of communication links like Wi-Fi & cellular networks, interferes with GPS reception, and can disable control systems or drones. It is a common tactic in conflict zones used to blind or disorient opponents because it does not require sophisticated hacking techniques, but rather just powerful transmission equipment.⁵⁵

Spoofing, on the other hand, is a cyberattack in which an adversary impersonates a trusted or legitimate source to deceive systems or users, often with the goal of gaining unauthorized access, spreading malware, or bypassing security controls.⁵⁶ In the space context, this can include GPS spoofing, where fake navigation signals mislead receivers into calculating incorrect positions. This potentially diverts ships or disrupts synchronized power grids. Spoofing can also occur through falsified network identifiers, which enables attackers to bypass defences or impersonate legitimate devices and users.⁵⁷ The examples of cyber attacks mentioned above focus on attacks on the communication systems. Sometimes, cyber attacks can be done by attacking the ground components of space infrastructure. Hacking ground stations in this regard represents another vector where attackers infiltrate the terrestrial control centres that manage satellites, often through vulnerabilities in outdated software or supply chains. This allows them to commandeer orbits or data flows. It can also be done by deploying malware, which is the insidious code that can be injected into satellite systems to corrupt data, alter commands, or even render hardware useless. This is much like a virus spreading through a network, except that this takes place in the vacuum of space, where repairs are not only exponentially more difficult but also more expensive.

Most dual-use satellites began as purely civilian systems for specific civilian purposes, but their economic efficiency has led States and commercial operators to increasingly rely on them for both civilian and military functions.⁵⁸ These are especially vulnerable to cyberattacks because many were built with functionality, affordability, and commercial accessibility in mind rather than resilience against sophisticated digital threats.⁵⁹ Their civilian–military nature makes them extremely attractive targets as they can degrade military communications or surveillance capabilities. This creates a strategic incentive for adversaries to strike them as they are systems that offer maximum impact with minimal risk. A cyber attack on a space system may not meet the threshold of an armed attack in the kinetic sense traditionally envisioned by the UN Charter to warrant self-defence under Article 51. Unlike traditional combat, there is no consensus on whether or not such actions warrant self-defence.⁶⁰ The difficulty of attributing these attacks further emboldens malicious actors. Cyber operations are frequently routed through proxy servers, botnets, or encrypted channels, masking their origin and complicating assessment across borders and jurisdictions. Because satellite operations involve multiple states, private companies, and international regulatory bodies, tracing responsibility with the level of certainty required for legal or diplomatic action is extremely challenging. This ambiguity creates a permissive environment where attackers rely on plausible deniability, allowing them to

⁵⁵ Sokolov, V., Skladannyi, P., & Platonenko, A. (2023). Jump-stay jamming attack on Wi-Fi systems. In *Proceedings of the 2023 IEEE 18th International Conference on Computer Science and Information Technologies (CSIT)* (pp. 1–5). IEEE. <https://doi.org/10.1109/CSIT61576.2023.10324031>.

⁵⁶ Babu, P., Bhaskari, L., & Satyanarayana, C. H. (2011). A comprehensive analysis of spoofing. *International Journal of Advanced Computer Sciences and Applications*. <https://doi.org/10.14569/IJACSA.2010.010623>.

⁵⁷ Ibid.

⁵⁸ Sommer, S. (2019). The legality of targeting dual-use satellites under the jus ad bellum and the jus in bello. GRIN Verlag. <https://www.grin.com/document/506730>.

⁵⁹ Ibid.

⁶⁰ Cornish, P. (Ed.) (2021). *The Oxford Handbook of Cyber Security*. Oxford University Press. <https://doi.org/10.1093/oxfordhb/9780198800682.001.0001>.

disrupt critical services, manipulate data, or degrade military capability without triggering immediate or proportionate responses.

There are many real-world incidents where these vulnerabilities have been exploited. During the 2022 Russian invasion of Ukraine, a cyberattack on the Viasat KA-SAT network disabled thousands of satellite modems, which severed Ukrainian military communications and affected civilian infrastructure across Europe.⁶¹ Persistent jamming and spoofing of satellite services, particularly targeting Starlink terminals supporting Ukrainian operations, became the defining features of the conflict.⁶² Similar patterns have emerged in the Middle East, where widespread GPS spoofing has become a significant and growing threat to civilian air and maritime transport, with an increasing number of incidents reported near conflict zones and strategic waterways.⁶³ Importantly, many of these attacks remain below the threshold of an “armed attack” under Article 51 of the UN Charter. Because they do not involve kinetic force or direct physical destruction, states often hesitate to classify them as acts that justify self-defence. Whether this needs reconsideration is addressed in the subsequent sections of this paper. This legal grey zone further increases the attractiveness of targeting dual-use satellites since adversaries can inflict substantial strategic harm while avoiding the legal and political consequences associated with more overt or escalatory forms of aggression.

4. INTERNATIONAL LEGAL FRAMEWORK

Outer space exploration and use have progressively developed in recent years, which has led to the development of an international legal regime to govern that development. The use of outer space is therefore primarily governed by international law and international space instruments. This section will look at all the frameworks in international law that govern the use of space. This includes frameworks both in the *lex generalis* of the UN Charter and customary international law principles and in the *lex spatialis* of space law. There are five international treaties that directly govern activities taking place in outer space.⁶⁴ Of them, the Treaty on Principles Governing the Activities of States in the Exploration and Use of Outer Space including the Moon and Other Celestial Bodies, also known as the 1967 Outer Space Treaty (OST), is most foundational and therefore most relevant to wartime activities on Earth. It sets the foundational tone for how nations should behave while using or exploring space.

The OST designates outer space as the “*province of all mankind*,” requiring that its exploration and use should be carried out for the benefit and in the interests of all States.⁶⁵ It further prohibits national appropriation of outer space “*by claim of sovereignty, by means of use or occupation, or by any other means*”, preventing States from asserting exclusive control over orbits or celestial bodies.⁶⁶ The Treaty also requires that activities in outer space be carried out with due regard to the interests of other States

⁶¹ CyberPeace Institute. (n.d.). *Case Study: Viasat*. CyberPeace Institute. Retrieved November 29, 2025, from <https://cyberconflicts.cyberpeaceinstitute.org/law-and-policy/cases/viasat>.

⁶² Mozur, P., & Satariano, A. (2024, May 24). *Russia, in new push, increasingly disrupts Ukraine's Starlink service*. *The New York Times*. <https://www.nytimes.com/2024/05/24/technology/ukraine-russia-starlink.html>.

⁶³ Lemos, R. (2025, April 17). *GPS spoofing attacks spike in Middle East, Southeast Asia*. Dark Reading.

⁶⁴ Treaty on Principles Governing the Activities of States in the Exploration and Use of Outer Space, including the Moon and Other Celestial Bodies, Agreement on the Rescue of Astronauts, the Return of Astronauts and the Return of Objects Launched into Outer Space, Convention on International Liability for Damage Caused by Space Objects, Convention on Registration of Objects Launched into Outer Space & the Agreement Governing the Activities of States on the Moon and Other Celestial Bodies.

⁶⁵ Outer Space Treaty, Art. I.

⁶⁶ Outer Space Treaty, Art. II.

and that consultations be undertaken if a State's activities are potentially harmful.⁶⁷ It additionally incorporates general international law into space governance by requiring that activities be conducted in accordance with international law, and that includes the Charter of the United Nations.⁶⁸ This provision is particularly important for dual-use satellites, whose civilian and military functions may raise concerns about compliance with the UN Charter's rules on the use of force, non-intervention, and peaceful settlement of disputes.

With respect to militarisation and security, the OST prohibits the placement of nuclear weapons or any other weapons of mass destruction in orbit or on celestial bodies.⁶⁹ While it does not expressly prohibit all military activities in space, its object and purpose support the normative expectation of peaceful use and the prevention of destabilizing conduct. Destabilising conduct can be understood as non-aggressive or non-hostile conduct.⁷⁰ These obligations are strengthened by the UN Charter, which applies fully to outer space.⁷¹ The Charter prohibits the threat or use of force against the territorial integrity or political independence of any State.⁷² The exception to this is contained in Article 51 of the UN Charter on the right to self-defence, but even this is limited to circumstances of an armed attack.⁷³ This constraint is especially relevant for cyber or electronic interference with dual-use satellites, since many such acts may fall below the threshold of an armed attack and therefore would not justify forcible countermeasures.⁷⁴ The Charter also emphasizes the peaceful settlement of disputes,⁷⁵ which applies equally to disagreements arising from harmful interference, in space activities or ground conflict.

The responsibility of States for activities in outer space is set out explicitly in the OST. States bear international responsibility for national activities in outer space, whether carried out by governmental or non-governmental entities,⁷⁶ and they are required to authorize and continuously supervise private operators.⁷⁷ This is crucial for dual-use satellites, which are increasingly designed, operated, or financed by private actors for civilian duties, but they simultaneously serve military, intelligence, or strategic functions. Liability for damage caused by space objects is also attributed to launching States under the OST,⁷⁸ a principle elaborated in the 1972 *Convention on International Liability for Damage Caused by Space Objects* (Liability Convention), which imposes absolute liability for damage on the surface of the Earth and fault-based liability for damage occurring elsewhere in space.⁷⁹ These rules apply regardless of whether the satellite's use at the time was civilian, commercial, or military.

⁶⁷ Outer Space Treaty, Art. IX.

⁶⁸ Outer Space Treaty, Art. III.

⁶⁹ Outer Space Treaty, Art IV.

⁷⁰ Schmitt, M. N. (2006). *International law and military operations in space*. Max Planck Yearbook of United Nations Law, 10, 89–125.

⁷¹ Article III of the 1967 OST stipulates that states must conduct space activities, including exploring the moon and other celestial bodies, in accordance with international law and the UN Charter to promote peace and security.

⁷² UN Charter, Art. 2(4).

⁷³ The travaux préparatoires of the UN Charter affirm that a prohibited 'use of force' in Art. 2 (4) refers to armed force and not to economic or other forms of coercion. See <https://opil.ouplaw.com/display/10.1093/law-epil/9780199231690/law-9780199231690-e2267>.

⁷⁴ Cornish, P. (Ed.) (2021), *supra note 60*.

⁷⁵ UN Charter, Art. 33.

⁷⁶ UN Charter, Art. VI.

⁷⁷ Ibid.

⁷⁸ Outer Space Treaty, Art. VII.

⁷⁹ United Nations. (1972). *Convention on International Liability for Damage Caused by Space Objects* (Liability Convention). United Nations Treaty Series, 961, 185.

Also, there are other core treaties that are applicable here, which add sector-specific rules. The 1968 Rescue Agreement sets out obligations to assist astronauts in distress and return spacecraft,⁸⁰ while the 1975 *Convention on Registration of Objects Launched into Outer Space* (Registration Convention) requires States to maintain national registries of space objects and provide orbital and functional information to the UN Secretary General about the general function of a space object. Specifically, Paragraph 1(d) of Article IV calls for a description of the space object's function, which aims to enhance transparency and traceability.⁸¹ For dual-use satellites whose military features may not be openly declared, the registration requirement contributes to confidence-building and helps prevent miscalculation. The 1979 Moon Agreement, though ratified by a few States,⁸² seeks to govern the exploitation of celestial resources and reinforces the non-appropriation principle.⁸³

Whereas the International Court of Justice (ICJ) has not issued space-specific judgments, its jurisprudence in several of its decisions and opinions has affirmed certain principles that are relevant to space activities, more so in the context of international responsibility and the application of the use-of-force regime. In *Nicaragua v. United States*⁸⁴ and the *Advisory Opinion on Nuclear Weapons*,⁸⁵ the ICJ confirmed that the UN Charter and customary international law apply to all domains, including new technological environments. The Court's reasoning that States may not use force or intervene coercively through indirect means has been invoked in contemporary debates about whether cyber operations against satellites could violate Article 2(4) or constitute unlawful intervention.⁸⁶ These decisions bridge the *lex generalis* of international law with the *lex spatialis* of space law contained in treaties, which reinforces the basic principle that space is not a law-free zone. It is important to recall that all 193 member states of the UN are signatories to the ICJ, and this means that in instances of conflict, the ICJ will most likely soon pronounce itself on matters regarding the use of space.

Building on this jurisprudence, several soft-law frameworks and expert manuals help interpret how existing rules apply to modern satellite operations and dual-use systems. Key among these are UN General Assembly resolutions calling for the prevention of an arms race in outer space⁸⁷ and the 2013

⁸⁰ United Nations. (1968). *Agreement on the Rescue of Astronauts, the Return of Astronauts, and the Return of Objects Launched into Outer Space* (Rescue Agreement). United Nations Treaty Series, vol. 672, p. 119.

⁸¹ United Nations. (1975). *Convention on Registration of Objects Launched into Outer Space* (Registration Convention). United Nations Treaty Series, 1023, 15. (Opened for signature January 14, 1975; entered into force September 15, 1976.)

⁸² United Nations. (1979). *Agreement Governing the Activities of States on the Moon and Other Celestial Bodies* (Moon Agreement). United Nations Treaty Series, 1363, 3. (Adopted December 5, 1979; opened for signature December 18, 1979; entered into force July 11, 1984) ; It is important to note that only 18 states are signatories to this Agreement and in 2023, Saudi Arabia informed the Secretary General of the UN of its intention to withdraw from the agreement. See Wedenig, S.-M., & Nelson, J. W. (2023, January 26). *The Moon Agreement: Hanging by a thread?* McGill Institute of Air and Space Law. <https://www.mcgill.ca/iasl/article/moon-agreement-hanging-thread>.

⁸³ Article 11(2) of the Moon Agreement provides that: “*The Moon is not subject to national appropriation by any claim of sovereignty, by means of use or occupation, or by any other means*”.

⁸⁴ International Court of Justice. (1986). *Case Concerning Military and Paramilitary Activities in and against Nicaragua (Nicaragua v. United States)*, ICJ Rep. 1986, p. 14.

⁸⁵ International Court of Justice. (1996). *Legality of the Threat or Use of Nuclear Weapons (Advisory Opinion)*, ICJ Rep. 1996, p. 226.

⁸⁶ Pustorino, P. (2018, September 30). *The principle of non-intervention in recent non-international armed conflicts*. QIL – Questions of International Law / QDI. <https://www.qil-qdi.org/principle-non-intervention-recent-non-international-armed-conflicts/>.

⁸⁷ UN General Assembly. (2024, October 12). *Prevention of an arms race in outer space (A/RES/79/19)*. United Nations. Also see the UN General Assembly. (2024, October 12). *Further practical measures for the prevention of an arms race in outer space (A/RES/79/21)*. United Nations.

UN Group of Governmental Experts report on transparency and confidence-building measures in outer space activities.⁸⁸ This report, adopted by consensus, recommended actions such as sharing information on space policies, providing pre-launch notifications, conducting cooperative data exchanges, and allowing voluntary visits to space launch sites. Its goal was to reduce the risk of misunderstanding and mistrust among spacefaring nations by enhancing dialogue and promoting responsible behavior.

Finally, the United Nations Committee on the Peaceful Uses of Outer Space (UNCOPUOS) has developed important *Long-term Sustainability Guidelines* (LTS) of outer space activities.⁸⁹ These guidelines encourage States to adopt national regulatory frameworks,⁹⁰ mitigate space debris, protect the space environment,⁹¹ share information on space objects, avoid harmful interference, and enhance cybersecurity and resilience of space infrastructure.⁹² They are directly relevant to dual-use satellites, whose dense integration into communications, navigation, and intelligence networks makes them particularly sensitive to both physical and cyber risks. The LTS Guidelines emphasise transparency, due regard, and responsible behaviour, which are core principles that help ensure that dual-use activities do not escalate geopolitical tensions or undermine the safety and sustainability of the shared orbital environment.

Complementing the space law regime is the Law of Armed Conflict (International Humanitarian Law (IHL)), which applies during international armed conflicts and brings the core principles of distinction, proportionality, and necessity to any military operation, including cyber operations that affect space systems. The principle of distinction, drawn from Additional Protocol I (AP I) to the Geneva Conventions,⁹³ requires parties to differentiate between civilian objects and military objectives. In reality, a dual-use satellite may become a military objective if its functions make an effective contribution to military action, as seen in the operational use of commercial satellites in the Ukraine conflict discussed above. Even so, any attack must satisfy the principle of proportionality, which prohibits operations where expected civilian harm would be excessive relative to the anticipated military advantage.⁹⁴ Cyber operations on space systems complicate this assessment, since non-kinetic effects such as data corruption or widespread service outages may not cause physical destruction but can still trigger significant civilian consequences. The principle of necessity further limits military operations to those required to achieve a legitimate military objective.⁹⁵ These rules, which are affirmed by the ICRC and reflected in the Tallinn Manual 2.0, apply to cyber operations during armed conflict, including those targeting space systems. However, they do not apply in peacetime, leaving cyber interference that falls below the UN Charter's "armed attack" threshold outside LOAC's governance.⁹⁶

⁸⁸ Group of Governmental Experts on Transparency and Confidence-Building Measures in Outer Space Activities. (2013). *Transparency & confidence-building measures in outer space activities* (Report to the Secretary-General, A/68/189). United Nations.

⁸⁹ United Nations Office for Outer Space Affairs. (2021). *Guidelines for the Long-Term Sustainability of Outer Space Activities of the Committee on the Peaceful Uses of Outer Space* (ST/SPACE/79). United Nations. https://www.unoosa.org/documents/pdf/PromotingSpaceSustainability/Publication_Final_English_June2021.pdf

⁹⁰ *Supra note* 89, Guideline A.1.

⁹¹ *Supra note* 89, Guideline B.3 & Guideline B.9

⁹² *Supra note* 89, Guideline C.1 & Guideline C.2

⁹³ International Committee of the Red Cross. (1977). *Protocol Additional to the Geneva Conventions of 12 August 1949, and relating to the Protection of Victims of International Armed Conflicts (Protocol I)*, Article 48. 1125 U.N.T.S. 3. <https://ihl-databases.icrc.org/en/ihl-treaties/api-1977>.

⁹⁴ AP I, Art. 51.

⁹⁵ AP I, Art. 52(2).

⁹⁶ *Supra note* 73.

Upon proper analysis of this legal framework in its entirety in the context of cyber attacks on satellite systems, a legal grey zone becomes apparent. The blending of civilian and military functions in the use of satellites strains traditional classifications, since dual-use satellites remain permissible under the OST as long as they align with peaceful purposes as required by Article IV of the OST. However, they lose civilian protection under the law of armed conflict once they directly support military operations during an armed conflict. The Tallinn Manual adopts this same logic for cyber operations involving dual-use systems, requiring proportionality analyses that account for civilian reliance on those satellites. The problem is that neither the OST nor the law of armed conflict explicitly addresses cyber operations in space. The OST predates the digital era and focuses on physical activities, while the application of the law of armed conflict to non-kinetic cyber effects remains unsettled. As a result, cyber actions such as spoofing or signal manipulation may cause serious disruption of civilian life and essential services yet fall below the thresholds that would clearly trigger the law of armed conflict or self-defence under the UN Charter. This legal ambiguity creates opportunities for misuse, enabling States or private actors to exploit dual-use vulnerabilities, avoid clear attribution, and operate in a grey zone where accountability is difficult and interpretations of the law remain fluid.

5. IMPLICATIONS, ADEQUACY OF CURRENT NORMS AND RECOMMENDATIONS

The dual-use nature of civilian satellites has many implications for the observance of international law, state security concerns and geopolitical tensions. Most of these implications are tied to the inadequacy of the existing laws and norms around the matter. This section will therefore partly focus on exploring those implications, initially, before then focusing on making recommendations to address any challenges.

Firstly, the dual-use nature of satellites significantly heightens escalation risks in cyber-enabled conflict. Because many commercial satellites provide essential military support functions such as communications and navigation, cyber operations against them present an opportunity for adversaries to degrade military capability without resorting to kinetic force.⁹⁷ Actions like jamming, spoofing, or malware insertion can temporarily neutralize military advantages while remaining below the threshold of an armed attack under Article 51 of the UN Charter.⁹⁸ This makes dual-use satellites attractive targets in armed conflicts, more so for countries having developed space capabilities to undertake these attacks. The financial and digital divide among nations exacerbates the issue. Advanced economies may possess the tools to detect, mitigate, and recover from cyber incidents, but many emerging space actors do not. This disparity makes some nations disproportionately vulnerable and, perhaps unintentionally, conduits for cyberattacks launched through compromised assets.⁹⁹ Here, the risk of miscalculation is substantial as states may perceive interference with critical satellites as preparations for broader hostilities, which narrows the window for diplomatic de-escalation.¹⁰⁰ As AI-enabled cyber capabilities spread, the speed and automation of attacks may further compress decision-making time and increase the prospect that a limited cyber intrusion is interpreted as the

⁹⁷ Goran Pavlović. (2025, May 24). *Cybersecurity in the context of international space agreements*. TheSIGN.media. Accessible via: <https://www.thesign.media/blog/cybersecurity-in-the-context-of-international-space-agreements>.

⁹⁸ Cornish, P. (Ed.) (2021), *supra* note 60.

⁹⁹ Pavlović. (2025, May 24), *supra* note 97.

¹⁰⁰ Comtech Telecommunications Corp. (2025, November 21). *Cybersecurity in the space domain: Why it's time to stop leaving the front door unlocked*. <https://www.comtech.com/general/2025/11/21/cybersecurity-in-the-space-domain-why-its-time-to-stop-leaving-the-front-door-unlocked/>.

opening move of a wider conflict, particularly given the close integration between commercial satellites and critical infrastructure on Earth.¹⁰¹ Similarly, a cyber operation that causes significant disruption to satellite capabilities may be interpreted as an unlawful use of force, or even an armed attack, depending on its scale and effects. The 2022 Viasat incident illustrated how cyber interference with a dual-use satellite system can produce simultaneous military and civilian impacts while provoking immediate countermeasures.¹⁰² Grey-zone operations are especially destabilizing because they are intentionally designed to fall short of clear thresholds. Yet misperceptions about the intent behind a cyber intrusion, especially in tense geopolitical environments, could trigger rapid escalation.¹⁰³ It has been argued that without clearer norms for satellite cyber operations, these dynamics weaken traditional deterrence models and leave States with few predictable tools for crisis management.¹⁰⁴

Secondly, persistent cyber vulnerabilities erode global confidence in commercial space services.¹⁰⁵ Public trust suffers when cyber incidents in the form of attacks cause spillover effects across essential civilian sectors, including finance, agriculture, transport, and emergency services. Even brief outages can produce huge economic losses in the billions, which raises questions about the reliability of private satellite operators.¹⁰⁶ As reliance on global satellite networks grows, States may choose to develop sovereign systems, for security concerns, which will have the impact of fragmenting the international market and weakening collaborative ventures such as environmental monitoring and global broadband initiatives. This trend towards fragmentation of the global satellite market will primarily be driven by national security concerns and the desire for assured access to vital communication and data services.

It is therefore important that targeted action is taken to address these challenges posed by the grey zone so as to limit the potential harms. This section will now turn to making policy and governance recommendations to achieve this.

Firstly, to mitigate the cybersecurity risks of dual-use satellites, establishing universal cybersecurity standards for space operations is critical to creating a resilient, equitable, and secure orbital ecosystem. For example, recent U.S. initiatives signal growing momentum for harmonized efforts to address the patchwork of existing frameworks, to avoid leaving commercial and international

¹⁰¹ Puscas, I. (2023). *AI and international security: Understanding the risks and paving the path for confidence-building measures* (pp. 41–45). United Nations Institute for Disarmament Research (UNIDIR). https://www.unidir.org/wp-content/uploads/2023/10/UNIDIR_AI-international-security_understanding_risks_paving_the_path_for_confidence-building_measures.pdf.

¹⁰² Mura, A. (2025), *supra* note 13.

¹⁰³ Pavlović. (2025, May 24), *supra* note 97.

¹⁰⁴ Global Commission on the Stability of Cyberspace. (n.d.). *GCSC norms*. The Hague Centre for Strategic Studies (HCSS). <https://hcss.nl/gcsc-norms/>.

¹⁰⁵ IndustrialCyber. (2024). *With space infrastructure at risk, experts call for cybersecurity-by-design, tight governance & supply-chain accountability*. IndustrialCyber. <https://industrialcyber.co/threat-landscape/with-space-infrastructure-at-risk-experts-call-for-cybersecurity-by-design-tight-governance-supply-chain-accountability/>.

¹⁰⁶ Bello, A.-W., Wonuola, I., Obunadike, C., Izundu, A., & Izundu, J. (2025). Assessing the impact of cybersecurity incidents on financial losses and user exposure in the global financial sector (2015–2024). *International Journal of Science and Research Archive*, 16, 489–504. <https://doi.org/10.30574/ijrsra.2025.16.1.2037>.

operators vulnerable.¹⁰⁷ Drawing from NIST's Cybersecurity Framework for space systems,¹⁰⁸ these standards should mandate scalable, risk-based measures such as regular third-party audits, AI-driven real-time threat detection, and quantum-resistant encryption to counter sophisticated threats like spoofing, ransomware, or signal jamming. Unlike terrestrial systems, satellites operate in a uniquely unforgiving environment, which then requires tailored protocols that account for limited onboard processing and long operational lifespans. In this regard, a tiered approach that starts with baseline requirements for critical functions like navigation, telemetry, and communications would accommodate diverse operators, from resource-constrained start-ups to emerging space nations in the Global South. First is the aspect of prioritizing secure-by-design principles for new satellites, which could be incentivized through insurance discounts or regulatory fast-tracking.¹⁰⁹ These satellite designs, which are built with security in mind, are very important in mitigating the harms of cyber intrusions in space activities of both states and private actors.

On the other hand, overly prescriptive rules risk stifling innovation or excluding smaller players, so standards should evolve through iterative feedback, piloted via public-private partnerships. To achieve this, international coordination is vital. In this regard, UNCOUOS, building on its debris mitigation guidelines,¹¹⁰ is well-positioned to convene stakeholders and integrate cyber standards into existing space governance frameworks. This inclusive process would counter region-centric biases,¹¹¹ ensuring buy-in from Global South nations like Nigeria and those from the East like China and Russia, whose growing space programs demand equitable representation. To drive adoption, compliance could be tied to access to shared orbital resources or funding from multilateral space initiatives. This raises the security baseline across all operators, deterring attacks by increasing the cost and complexity for adversaries while fostering trust in commercial and international collaborations.

It is important to enhance transparency and confidence-building measures (TCBMs) among states. Bolstering this framework involves creating mechanisms for open communication that demystify intentions and reduce the paranoia fuelling escalation in space. Transparency and confidence-building measures are a set of tools designed to display, predict and discipline states' behaviour with respect to maintaining the security of space.¹¹² TCBMs, long used in arms control to build trust, could adapt to cyber threats through voluntary reporting of incidents, pre-notification of satellite maneuvers, or joint

¹⁰⁷ Trump, D. J. (2020). Memorandum on space policy directive-5—Cybersecurity principles for space systems. The White House. <https://trumpwhitehouse.archives.gov/presidential-actions/memorandum-space-policy-directive-5-cybersecurity-principles-space-systems/>.

¹⁰⁸ National Institute of Standards and Technology (NIST). (2022). Satellite ground segment: Applying the cybersecurity framework to satellite command and control (NISTIR 8401). U.S. Department of Commerce. <https://csrc.nist.gov/pubs/ir/8401/final>.

¹⁰⁹ Ingols, K., et al. (2015). Guidelines for secure small satellite design and implementation. Lincoln Laboratory, Massachusetts Institute of Technology. <https://www.ll.mit.edu/sites/default/files/publication/doc/guidelines-secure-small-satellite-design-ingols-lsp-249.pdf>.

¹¹⁰ United Nations Office for Outer Space Affairs. (2021). *Guidelines for the long-term sustainability of outer space activities of the Committee on the Peaceful Uses of Outer Space (ST/SPACE/79)*. United Nations. https://www.unoosa.org/documents/pdf/PromotingSpaceSustainability/Publication_Final_English_June2021.pdf

¹¹¹ Such as U.S. or EU-centric biases.

¹¹² Robinson, M. (2016). Transparency and confidence-building measures for space security. *Space Policy*, 37, 134.

exercises simulating cyber responses, as explored in analyses of space security measures.¹¹³ For instance, platforms for sharing threat data, similar to those in cyberspace CBMs could prevent misattributions, where a glitch could, for example, have been mistaken for an attack. This draws from UN Open-Ended Working Group on Security of and in the Use of Information and Communications Technologies discussions on responsible behaviours that emphasize transparency to deter malicious acts.¹¹⁴ The goal is to avoid the weaponisation of transparency in a tense geopolitical environment, whereby if one side shares too much, it might expose vulnerabilities. Therefore, any such measures should be reciprocal and phased, starting with low-stakes information like orbital parameters before advancing to cyber-specific disclosures. Bilateral agreements, like those between the U.S. and allies, also help to scale to multilateral forums, fostering a culture of openness that rebuilds global trust eroded by incidents like GPS spoofing in conflict zones.¹¹⁵ By integrating TCBMs, states can be able to mitigate potential escalation threats and turn potential adversaries into partners in safeguarding shared orbital commons.

Additionally, it is important to advance the international treaty and soft law mechanisms. This can be in the form of voluntary codes of conduct, targeted treaty amendments, or dedicated protocols that provide a dynamic pathway to modernize the 1967 Outer Space Treaty (OST) and laws of armed conflict for the cyber domain. This will help to address persistent interpretive gaps that adversaries exploit. A pivotal starting point is a global code of conduct for space cyber operations. This can be modelled on the Hague Code of Conduct against Ballistic Missile Proliferation, which is a 2002 voluntary, politically binding international agreement with over 140 subscribing states aimed at preventing the spread of, and curbing the development, testing, and deployment of, Weapons of Mass Destruction-capable ballistic missiles.¹¹⁶ This Code of Conduct mandates transparency measures among subscribing states, such as pre-launch notifications and annual policy declarations in Section 4(a) iii of the Code. A similar code for cybersecurity in space could mandate real-time reporting of cyber incidents, prohibitions on targeting civilian satellite functions, and mandatory cooperation on attribution to deter deniability. This soft instrument would prioritize consensus-building on foundational terminology and classifications, such as defining non-kinetic attacks, e.g., jamming, spoofing, or malware injection, as equivalent to armed attacks under Article 51 of the UN Charter when they cause physical damage, disrupt critical infrastructure, or scale to coercive effects. This would then help in clarifying when it is right to trigger self-defence rights.¹¹⁷ The other instrument that could offer guidance in building such a code is the Tallinn Manual 2.0.¹¹⁸ The clarifications drawn from this framework for cyber operations would resolve ambiguities in the peaceful purposes clause in Article IV of the OST. This will prevent escalatory miscalculations, like those in the 2022 Viasat

¹¹³ United Nations Office for Disarmament Affairs. (2022). *TCBMs for a sustainable outer space* (Speaker notes, 7 June 2018), <https://documents.unoda.org/wp-content/uploads/2022/03/180607-TCBMs-CD-Raji-Speaker-Notes.pdf>.

¹¹⁴ See generally, Open-Ended Working Group on Security of and in the Use of Information and Communications Technologies (OEWG). (2024). *How information sharing contributes to security and stability in cyberspace: Examples from regional Points of Contact networks* [Working paper]. United Nations Office for Disarmament Affairs. https://docs-library.unoda.org/Open-Ended_Working_Group_on_Information_and_Communications_Technologies_-_2021/Final_28112024_-_Confidence_Builders_Info_Sharing.pdf.

¹¹⁵ Robinson, M. (2016), *supra note* 112.

¹¹⁶ United Nations General Assembly. (2005). *The Hague Code of Conduct against Ballistic Missile Proliferation*. A/RES/60/62.

¹¹⁷ Lewis, P. (2019). Create a global code of conduct for outer space. *Chatham House*. <https://www.chathamhouse.org/2019/06/create-global-code-conduct-outer-space>.

¹¹⁸ Schmitt, M. N. (2017). *Tallinn Manual 2.0 on the International Law Applicable to Cyber Operations* (2nd ed.). Cambridge University Press.

cyberattack.¹¹⁹ These mechanisms not only fill voids in the outdated frameworks but also cultivate a normative ecosystem that reduces misperception risks, fosters verifiable restraint, and positions space as a shared sanctuary rather than a contested battlefield.

6. CONCLUSION

The cybersecurity perils and legal implications of dual-use satellites in armed conflicts have been examined in this research. It has highlighted the inherent vulnerabilities arising from the integration of civilian space infrastructure into military operations, the challenges of attribution in cyber incidents, and the critical need to uphold principles of distinction, proportionality, and necessity under international humanitarian law. The analysis has also explored the strategic incentives for adversaries to exploit non-kinetic attacks, fuelled by the inadequacies of existing frameworks like the Outer Space Treaty and the Law of Armed Conflict in addressing cyber-specific threats. By incorporating these underexplored dimensions of the international legal regime, the research aims to contribute to the evolution of norms governing dual-use technologies, promoting equitable access to space while preserving strategic stability and protecting civilian functions.

As discussed, the orbital domain continues to become increasingly congested and contested every other day. However, the cyber risks to dual-use satellites remain a pressing concern that not only renders traditional boundaries ineffective but also tests the resilience of the current international legal systems on space. Ambiguity around the norms characterizing space cyber operations complicates determinations of whether non-kinetic disruptions such as spoofing, jamming, or malware injection qualify as armed attacks under Article 51 of the UN Charter or even whether they are violations of the OST's peaceful purposes clause in Article VI. This represents a significant lacuna in the legal architecture of the existing treaties, which are mainly foundational and do not address the emerging threats like AI-orchestrated attacks. This leaves room for miscalculation that could escalate into terrestrial disruptions with grave effects on navigation, finance, and disaster response.

The UNCOPOUS guidelines are some of the international efforts that attempt to address these vulnerabilities. However, a comprehensive response has proven elusive amid the rapid evolution of space technologies and the fragmentation of governance across state and non-state actors. There is promise in a new international convention dedicated to space cybersecurity, modelled perhaps on the Hague Code of Conduct, to foster consensus on definitions, prohibit targeting of civilian satellite functions, and mandate cooperation on attribution and resilience. This framework could be transparent, inclusive, and adaptable, facilitating multilateral collaboration, criminalizing grey-zone acts, and establishing enforcement mechanisms through arbitration or UN referrals. Such a convention would mark a pivotal advancement in securing the orbital commons as a domain for peaceful exploration. Therefore, it is imperative to re-evaluate and adapt the existing legal infrastructure or explore the creation of a specialized international body to effectively confront the unique challenges of dual-use satellites in cyber-enabled warfare.

¹¹⁹ Roscini, M. (2024). Law in orbit: International legal perspectives on cyberattacks targeting space systems. *Marine Policy*, 163, Article 105696. <https://www.sciencedirect.com/science/article/abs/pii/S0308596124000363>.